

Consumer-side dynamics in sustainability transitions: An Eco-SEIRN model of pro-environmental behaviour

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Abstract

This paper develops a dynamic model of the diffusion of pro-environmental consumer behaviour within sustainability transitions, driven by social interaction, media influence, and resistance to ecological communication. The proposed Eco-SEIRN framework distinguishes five consumer types – Susceptible, Exposed, Involved, Responsible Green, and Neglectful – reflecting different levels of environmental engagement and the possibility of persistent resistance.

Numerical simulations show that the system evolves toward a stylized pro-environmental steady state that is locally asymptotically stable under the model assumptions. A key result is that improving the ability of communication to reduce resistance among neglectful consumers has a substantially stronger impact than increasing campaign intensity. While media accelerate transition dynamics, long-run outcomes are primarily shaped by social reinforcement mechanisms and the visible presence of already engaged groups. The results indicate that sustainability transitions in consumption depend not only on message exposure but also on the capacity to overcome resistance and prevent the persistence or resurgence of neglectful attitudes, underscoring the importance of targeted, credible, and socially embedded communication strategies within sustainability transition governance.

Keywords: sustainability transitions, pro-environmental behavior, consumer segmentation, social influence, media effects, compartmental diffusion model

1 Introduction

Understanding the mechanisms that shape consumer attitudes toward green consumption is increasingly important in the context of climate change and sustainability. Individual consumption choices play a crucial role in determining environmental outcomes, and the diffusion of pro-environmental attitudes within society can significantly accelerate or hinder the transition toward more sustainable consumption patterns. In recent years, researchers have highlighted the role of social interactions, communication networks, and media exposure in shaping consumer perceptions and behaviors related to environmental responsibility.

While a growing body of research examines the determinants of pro-environmental attitudes and the diffusion of sustainable consumption, relatively little attention has been devoted to formal dynamic models that capture how such attitudes spread across society through interpersonal influence and media communication. Existing studies often analyze behavioral determinants using survey-based or econometric approaches, but fewer attempts have been made to represent these processes using dynamic compartmental models that explicitly describe transitions between different consumer attitudes over time.

Within sustainability transitions research, consumer-side dynamics remain important yet still insufficiently formalized (e.g. Bögel and Upham, 2018; Köhler et al., 2019). While recent studies emphasize that transitions require behavioural change, such processes are still only partially integrated into formal transition models. At the same time, households and consumers are increasingly recognized as relevant sites of agency in sustainability transitions (Berker et al., 2025). Building on this perspective, we treat pro-environmental consumption not as an isolated outcome of individual choice, but as a dynamic process of social diffusion through which ecological orientations can reinforce, slow down, or destabilize broader transition processes. In this sense, the Eco-SEIRN framework captures one behavioural layer of sustainability transitions, focusing on the co-evolution of awareness, resistance, social reinforcement, and media-mediated learning across consumer groups.

To operationalize this perspective, this paper proposes a novel mathematical framework inspired by the SEIR epidemiological model. The Eco-SEIRN model developed in this study describes the dynamics of the spread of pro-ecological attitudes in society by incorporating both social interactions and media communication, including the presence of resistance to ecological messaging and mechanisms through which such resistance can be reduced. The model integrates an existing segmentation approach from the literature, capturing different levels of ecological awareness and engagement among consumers. Using this framework, we analyze the mechanisms that drive the diffusion of sustainable consumption attitudes, examine the stationary states of the system and their stability, and perform numerical simulations to investigate how communication effectiveness and campaign intensity jointly shape behavioral dynamics. The model also speaks to recent concerns in sustainability transitions research about resistance, relapse, and backlash, by showing how weakly internalized ecological awareness may stagnate or erode under countervailing social influence.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature on the diffusion of pro-environmental attitudes and the role of media and social interactions in shaping sustainable consumption. Section 3 presents the consumer typologies and segmentation used in the model. Section 4 outlines the empirical context of pro-environmental attitudes in Poland, which motivates the calibration of the model. Section 5 introduces the Eco-SEIRN model. Section 6 provides a numerical analysis of the system's dynamics. Finally, Section 7 discusses the main conclusions, policy implications, and directions for future research.

2 Theoretical Background

The spread of consumer attitudes, including pro-environmental attitudes, is a complex phenomenon that can be analyzed from the perspectives of various disciplines, such as economics, sociology, psychology, and environmental science. This section provides a review of the literature on the mechanisms underlying the formation and diffusion of consumer attitudes and behaviors. Our approach is theoretically grounded in the Attitude-Behavior-Context (ABC) framework (Guagnano et al., 1995; Stern, 2000), which highlights the importance of contextual factors - such as social reinforcement and media influence - in shaping behavioral outcomes.

2.1 Diffusion of Innovations and Social Contagion

Understanding how innovations and social attitudes diffuse is key to analyzing consumer behavior change. These processes are complex and shaped by factors such as social network structures, the nature of innovation, and interpersonal dynamics. A foundational model in this area is the Bass model (Bass, 1969), which combines the effects of advertising and social influence, and has been widely applied - from technology markets to the spread of social norms. The concept of threshold distributions, introduced by Granovetter (1978), helps explain why some communities change rapidly while others evolve more slowly. The importance of central actors in social networks was later emphasized by Valente (1996), who showed that opinion leaders and well-connected individuals accelerate diffusion, while those on the periphery have limited impact. The concept of tipping points, introduced by Gladwell (2000) and building on Granovetter's model, highlights that social contagion often requires momentum before widespread change occurs. This is especially relevant for pro-environmental behaviors, where adoption may be slow until a critical mass is reached. Such dynamics stress the need to design interventions targeting key influencers to accelerate diffusion.

The theory of innovation diffusion, originally formulated by Rogers in 1962 and later elaborated (Rogers, 2003), explains differences in adoption speed through adopter types and specific characteristics of innovations - such as relative advantage, compatibility with existing values, and ease of testing. These factors are particularly relevant in the context of sustainable consumption, where they influence the acceptance of pro-environmental behaviors. The distinction between simple and complex contagion, as shown by Centola and Macy (2007), has important implications for pro-environmental diffusion. Simple contagions, such as gossip, require only single exposure, whereas complex ones - like adopting sustainable norms - depend on repeated interactions and reinforcement from multiple sources. This underscores the need for campaigns based on sustained and diversified social influence.

Recent research confirms that social diffusion mechanisms are equally relevant in the context of sustainable consumption. For instance, Z. Wang et al. (2024) empirically examined how pro-environmental consumption diffuses through social networks and found that peer effects significantly enhance the adoption of green innovative products. Likewise, Zeng et al. (2020) developed an agent-based model capturing the co-evolution between green technology diffusion and consumers' pro-environmental attitudes, showing that feedback loops between technological change and attitude formation accelerate the overall diffusion of sustainable behaviors.

Diffusion mechanisms in technological and environmental contexts highlight the importance of external interventions. Newell (2010) and Sierzechula et al. (2014) showed that public policies and financial incentives accelerate innovation adoption. Structural and financial support facilitates pro-sustainability behaviors and helps normalize them - for example, through subsidies for electric vehicles or renewable energy. Wüstenhagen et al. (2007) showed that innovation adoption depends not only on demographics, cultural context, and technology access but also on attitude shifts, which

often lag behind technological change. This finding aligns with Aral et al. (2009), who distinguished between social contagion and homophily, showing that individual choices stem from both social influence and preexisting group similarities.

Building on these insights, Namazova (2025) emphasizes that social influence operates across both offline and digital domains, shaping individual preferences and accelerating the diffusion of sustainable norms through social networks. Her synthesis shows that peer groups and opinion leaders act as amplifiers of collective engagement, translating social approval into behavioral contagion in sustainability adoption.

Communication channels, including digital platforms, play an increasingly important role in the diffusion of social attitudes. Romero et al. (2011) and Bakshy et al. (2012) showed that weak ties expand information reach, while strong ties encourage deeper engagement. Hartmann et al. (2025) found that visual platforms like Instagram effectively promote ecological ideas through images and short videos.

In the context of our article, which focuses on sustainable consumption, the theories and models discussed above provide a solid theoretical foundation. Adopting pro-environmental attitudes in society requires an understanding not only of the dynamics of social networks but also of the roles of opinion leaders, public policies, and the effectiveness of media messaging. Taken together, these studies suggest that pro-environmental attitudes may diffuse through mechanisms analogous to social contagion, driven by interpersonal influence, network structure, and mediated communication.

2.2 Determinants of Pro-Environmental Attitudes and Behavior

Pro-environmental consumer attitudes arise from complex interactions between internal factors – such as values, beliefs, and moral norms – and external influences like social and institutional pressures. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for designing effective strategies to promote sustainable behaviors. Consumers should therefore be viewed not only as individual decision-makers but also as members of communities shaped by broader socio-cultural contexts. Links between biospheric and altruistic values and environmental concern have been well established, with limited influence attributed to egoistic values (Stern and Dietz, 1994). These effects operate through social and moral norms, prompting action as a moral obligation toward others. As discussed by Wyss et al. (2022), the persistent “environmental paradox” – a gap between attitudes and behaviors – underscores the need for strategies that promote active engagement.

Further theoretical support comes from the value-belief-norm (VBN) theory, originally developed by Stern et al. (1999), which emphasizes the role of personal moral norms as key drivers of ecological behavior. Another widely applied framework is the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Ajzen (1985). According to TPB, an individual’s intention to perform a behavior is the most immediate predictor of action and is shaped by three key factors: (1) attitude toward the behavior, (2) perceived social norms, and (3) perceived behavioral control – that is, the belief in one’s ability to carry out the action. TPB is particularly useful in the context of green consumption, as it highlights that even favorable attitudes toward ecological behaviors may not result in action if consumers perceive barriers such as cost, accessibility, or lack of social support. The theory has been empirically validated across various domains, including environmental behaviors (Kaiser and Gutscher (2003)), and provides a strong theoretical foundation for modeling how internal motivation and external context interact in shaping consumer decisions. Both frameworks address the determinants of pro-environmental behavior from complementary perspectives – while VBN highlights moral obligations and internalized values, TPB focuses on cognitive and motivational processes underlying behavioral intentions.

Moral norms, perceived behavioral control, and a sense of responsibility have been identified as key determinants of pro-environmental intentions, as demonstrated in the meta-analysis by Bamberg and Möser (2007). Their findings suggest that strategies for promoting sustainable behavior should focus

on strengthening these psychological factors and enhancing individuals' awareness of environmental problems. This view is supported by Steg and Vlek (2009), who highlighted the importance of incorporating insights from environmental psychology into policy design. Findings by Fielding et al. (2008) indicate that identification with groups promoting ecological values significantly increases intentions to engage in environmental activism. Group identity functions as a motivational factor that strengthens pro-environmental commitment and translates concern into action. Moreover, shared social norms and the influence of engaged peers within such groups can further enhance individual willingness to participate in collective ecological initiatives.

Both internal factors (e.g., values, perceived moral norms) and external ones (e.g., social pressure, education) play equally important roles in shaping pro-environmental attitudes, as shown by Gifford and Nilson (2014) and Onel and Mukherjee (2016). Ecological behavior depends not only on individual awareness and knowledge but also on institutional and social support. Strengthening environmental education and improving public understanding of ecological issues can therefore foster more consistent pro-environmental actions. In this context, the European Commission report *Towards sustainable food consumption* (European Commission: Group of Chief Scientific Advisors and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2023) emphasizes that promoting sustainable attitudes and behaviors requires coherence among political, educational, and societal actions. An interdisciplinary approach integrating behavioral insights, policy measures, and communication strategies is essential to reduce adaptive barriers and accelerate the adoption of sustainable practices within society.

Empirical evidence highlights that pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors are shaped by diverse cultural, structural, and technological contexts. Nielsen et al. (2019) demonstrated that public responses to environmental regulations – such as plastic bag bans and levies – vary substantially across societies, reflecting differences in governance traditions, social norms, and policy acceptance. At the individual level, Islam et al. (2022) showed that transparent systems for evaluating the environmental impact of e-commerce products, such as the SEER platform, can reduce the attitude–behavior gap by increasing consumers' trust and perceived control over sustainable choices. From a systemic perspective, Leocata et al. (2023) developed a Markovian model of solar panel adoption in Italy, illustrating how cognitive biases (e.g., hyperbolic discounting) and social influence jointly determine the diffusion of green technologies. Together, these studies emphasize that fostering sustainable behavior requires multi-level interventions – combining regulatory measures, technological design, and behavioral insights to promote more consistent ecological engagement.

Recent technological innovations also support pro-environmental decision-making by helping consumers align their choices with sustainability values. Asikis et al. (2021) introduced a smartphone-based personal shopping assistant designed according to the principles of value-sensitive design. The system combines expert knowledge with collective intelligence to provide transparent and explainable product ratings, thereby promoting informed and responsible consumption. Field experiments in supermarkets demonstrated that users exposed to the assistant showed higher sustainability awareness and a measurable shift toward eco-friendly purchasing. Beyond individual benefits, such technologies enable retailers and producers to adjust their offerings to consumer values, fostering a bottom-up transition toward sustainable markets. This approach highlights the growing role of digital tools in bridging informational and cognitive barriers that often hinder pro-environmental behavior.

Pro-environmental attitudes arise from the intersection of psychological mechanisms, social influence, and structural incentives. Capturing these interdependencies within formal models offers a framework for understanding how individual awareness translates into collective sustainability outcomes.

2.3 Media Influence and Information Diffusion

Social media plays a crucial role in shaping pro-environmental attitudes, offering a platform for the dissemination of information, promotion of environmental actions, and engagement of consumers in sustainability issues. With their interactivity, extensive reach, and instant responsiveness, social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter have become effective tools for promoting ecological ideas. A diffusive logistic model proposed by F. Wang et al. (2012) illustrates how information of any type – including ecological content – propagates across online networks. Their model shows that message reach expands rapidly during early diffusion stages and stabilizes as audience saturation occurs. Such diffusion models help explain the dynamics of viral environmental campaigns, in which user-generated content (e.g., photos or videos of pro-environmental actions) amplifies collective engagement and reach.

Empirical research confirms that the influence of social media on pro-environmental behavior depends on the emotional tone, credibility, and framing of messages. As shown by Hartmann et al. (2025), exposure to greenfluencers' nature posts on Instagram strengthens users' connection with nature, increases climate concern, and enhances intentions to act pro-environmentally. Similarly, Sanford et al. (2023) demonstrated that emotional framing plays a decisive role in online environmental activism: messages expressing negative emotions, such as fear or anger, tend to generate higher engagement but may also evoke emotional fatigue that weakens sustained action. At the organizational level, Hart et al. (2024) found that environmental NGOs (non-governmental organizations) achieve greater user engagement when their posts emphasize environmental impacts or political threats rather than neutral information. Finally, Comella Romeu (2025) showed that the framing of climate issues can either deepen or bridge ideological divides – messages based on shared values and solution-oriented narratives foster constructive engagement, whereas alarmist or moralizing tones tend to polarize audiences. Together, these findings highlight that the effectiveness of social media in fostering ecological engagement relies on both the structural dynamics of information diffusion and the psychological mechanisms of message perception.

Complementing these findings, Meng et al. (2023) examined how exposure to environmental information on social media platforms such as WeChat and Xiaohongshu influences young adults' intentions to engage in pro-environmental actions. Their results showed that frequent exposure to credible environmental content enhances pro-environmental attitudes and perceived behavioral control, which in turn strengthen individuals' willingness to act – for example, by recycling, using public transport, or joining environmental groups. The study underscores the importance of sustained and trustworthy social media communication in transforming online awareness into tangible ecological behavior.

More recent studies continue to highlight the growing importance of social media in shaping pro-environmental and sustainable consumption behaviors. Alsaad et al. (2023) advanced this discussion by applying sensemaking theory to explain how user engagement with pro-environmental content on social media translates into behavioral intentions. Their study conceptualized engagement not merely as attention or exposure but as an active, meaning-making process in which users internalize feelings of care and responsibility toward the environment. This subjective sense of responsibility strengthens pro-environmental self-concept and guides subsequent behavioral intentions. Based on data from 581 social media users, the authors found that engagement with pro-environmental campaigns fosters cognitive, emotional, and behavioral commitment, confirming that online participation can transform awareness into meaningful ecological action. Earlier research by Bedard and Tolmie (2018) similarly demonstrated that social media usage and online interpersonal influence positively affect millennials' green purchase intentions, underscoring that digital interaction and peer influence remain central mechanisms driving sustainable consumption.

The broader role of the internet in promoting ecological awareness and behavior has been confirmed

by Xiao et al. (2022), who analyzed data from the China General Social Survey. Their results showed that frequent internet use positively influences both private and public pro-environmental behaviors, particularly among women and lower-income groups. The study identified three primary mechanisms underlying this effect: the dissemination of environmental information, encouragement of participation in collective ecological campaigns, and strengthening of social relationships that facilitate sustainable practices. These findings highlight the Internet’s potential to act as an enabling infrastructure for behavioral change, linking access to information with everyday ecological choices. While the internet facilitates ecological engagement, Anderson and Huntington (2017) found that online discussions about climate change can also foster polarization and hostility, as sarcasm and incivility – though relatively rare – tend to accompany politically charged or skeptical perspectives. Such interactions can polarize audiences and weaken the credibility of scientific messages, reducing the effectiveness of pro-environmental communication. Together, these studies demonstrate that the internet simultaneously amplifies opportunities for ecological engagement and exposes communication to ideological tension, requiring careful message framing and moderation to sustain constructive dialogue.

From a modeling perspective, Li and Li (2020) applied a logistic regression framework to predict how information spreads across social media platforms. Their model identified several key factors influencing message virality, including local socio-economic conditions, counter-rumor mechanisms, and environmental context. Although the study focused on the diffusion of water pollution rumors, the methodology offers valuable insights into how environmental information can propagate in digital spaces. Logistic regression and similar diffusion models can help forecast audience reach, evaluate the credibility of sources, and optimize campaign design to maximize the spread of pro-environmental messages.

A more formal approach to modeling the influence of mass and social media on behavior was developed by Misra et al. (2018), using an extended SIR (Susceptible-Infected-Recovered) framework. Their system of differential equations examined how advertising campaigns via television and social media affect the spread and containment of infectious diseases. The model accounts for repeated media exposure and differentiates public responses based on message intensity and type. While originally applied in epidemiological contexts, its structure offers a promising foundation for modeling the diffusion of ecological attitudes under the influence of targeted media communication.

A recent methodological advancement was introduced by H. Wang et al. (2020), who developed a framework for modeling information diffusion in online social networks using partial differential equations (PDEs). This approach extends beyond traditional empirical and ordinary differential equation models by capturing both spatial and temporal dimensions of social interactions. The authors employ reaction–diffusion equations and graph Laplacian methods to represent how information propagates across user clusters embedded in a Euclidean space. Such models reveal complex interaction dynamics between communities, allowing the identification of cooperation, competition, and feedback effects in information exchange. Although primarily applied to data from Twitter and Digg, the framework provides a powerful mathematical foundation for analyzing how pro-environmental ideas or attitudes spread within interconnected digital ecosystems.

Patterns of ecological engagement observed in social media reflect broader social mechanisms of communication and diffusion. Digital environments amplify and render visible the dynamics through which pro-environmental attitudes spread, stabilize, or fade within interconnected communities. Capturing these processes within analytical frameworks enables a systematic understanding of how individual awareness transforms into collective behavioral change.

Taken together, the literature discussed above highlights three key mechanisms shaping the diffusion of pro-environmental attitudes: interpersonal influence, heterogeneity in consumer attitudes, and the role of media communication. These insights motivate the structure of the model proposed in this paper. In particular, the segmentation of consumers into different behavioral categories provides the foundation

for the compartmental structure of the Eco-SEIRN framework. The consumer categories used in the model are discussed in the next section.

3 Consumer Segmentation and Behavioral Categories

To formally represent the diffusion of pro-environmental attitudes in society, it is necessary to distinguish different categories of consumers reflecting varying levels of ecological awareness and engagement. The segmentation applied in our model builds upon existing typologies proposed in the literature, yet emphasizes the dynamic nature of attitude change. While previous typologies often describe consumer groups in static terms, our classification is embedded in a SEIR-type framework that reflects transitions between behavioral states. This dynamic perspective allows us to capture not only differences in ecological engagement but also the mechanisms of movement between segments. The section combines a brief overview of established typologies with the rationale for our model-based adaptation.

3.1 Consumer Typologies in Existing Literature

Popular typologies in the literature on green consumption distinguish consumer groups by their environmental awareness, motivations, and engagement. These classifications provide a conceptual basis for our own typology, designed to analyze the dynamics of ecological attitudes. One of the earliest attempts to classify consumers in the eco-friendly market was the GfK Roper Green Gauge study from the late 1980s (Roper GfK, 1989). Based on large-scale survey data from American consumers, the study identified varying attitudes toward eco-friendly products, categorizing consumers by their willingness to engage in pro-environmental actions. It classified them into three groups: **True-blue Greens**, highly committed to environmental protection; **Grousers**, who acknowledge the importance of environmental issues but remain less motivated to act; and **Basic Browns**, who show little interest in environmental concerns.

Later editions of the Green Gauge reports introduced a more refined segmentation reflecting changes in environmental awareness and consumer motivations. In the synthesis of Green Gauge data covering the period 2010–2020, five environmental archetypes were identified: **Green inDeed**, representing highly committed environmentalists actively engaged in sustainable practices; **Glamour Green**, for whom sustainability partly functions as a social identity and status signal; **Carbon Cultured**, who express environmental concern but whose behaviors often lag behind their attitudes; **Green in Need**, individuals willing to adopt greener lifestyles but constrained by limited resources or knowledge; and **Jaded**, a skeptical group whose environmentally friendly behaviors are typically driven by external incentives rather than intrinsic motivation (GfK (2021)). Subsequent editions of the Green Gauge reports confirm the continued relevance of these consumer archetypes in the U.S. market and highlight evolving pathways toward sustainable consumption (GfK (2023)). This evolution of the Green Gauge typology illustrates how consumer segmentation frameworks have become more nuanced as environmental awareness and sustainability discourse have expanded over time.

Another influential segmentation approach was proposed by Ottman (1998), who classified consumers according to their readiness to adopt green practices. Drawing on market analysis and green marketing experience, three main groups were identified: **Loyal Green Consumers**, **Less Devoted Green Consumers**, and **Consumers Completely Unwilling to Change**. This typology offered valuable insights into the varying levels of commitment and motivation within the green consumer base. Building on previous work, a typology introduced by Straughan and Roberts (1999) focused on consumer engagement with green products. Based on survey data from U.S. consumers, three main groups were identified: **Loyal Green Consumers**, who consistently choose eco-friendly products; **Green**

Consumers Developing, who are gradually adopting sustainable practices; and **Conservative Consumers**, who resist changing their purchasing habits. This typology was influential in identifying demographic and psychological factors, such as environmental concern, perceived effectiveness, and altruism, that drive consumer behavior in the green market.

Later, Memery et al. (2005) proposed a more detailed segmentation of UK shoppers, identifying four consumer types based on survey data about green food products: **Advanced Green Consumers**, who are highly committed to sustainability; **Green Consumers in Transition**, who are starting to adopt eco-friendly products; **Traditional Consumers**, focused on conventional goods; and **Apathetic Consumers**, with little interest in environmental issues. Their typology provided valuable insights into the changing dynamics of consumer behavior and the factors influencing eco-friendly purchasing decisions.

A widely used typology in eco-friendly consumer behavior research divides consumers into four groups: **Black Consumers** (Non-ecological Consumers), **Grey Consumers** (Average Consumers), **Greyish Green Consumers** (Environmentally Friendly Consumers), and **Green Consumers** (Ecological Consumers). Introduced by Banyte et al. (2010) for the Lithuanian market, this typology reflects both environmental awareness and actual engagement with eco-friendly products. **Black Consumers** lack environmental awareness, **Grey Consumers** have limited knowledge but feel no responsibility for change, **Greyish Green Consumers** are motivated by health or social status, and **Green Consumers** are highly environmentally conscious, actively supporting eco-friendly products.

A well-known segmentation approach in green consumption research is the classification by Jaiswal et al. (2021), which distinguishes three consumer groups based on commitment to sustainable purchasing: **Keen Greens**, who consistently seek eco-friendly products regardless of price; **Moderate Greens**, who balance ecological concerns with financial considerations; and **Reluctant Greens**, who, despite being aware of environmental issues, prioritize convenience and price over sustainability. The distinction between green and non-green consumers in the Portuguese market was analyzed by do Paço et al. (2009). In a separate study, Verain et al. (2012) proposed a typology based on survey data from Dutch consumers, which differentiates consumers by their environmental awareness and engagement in sustainable consumption.

Although the specific labels vary, typical segments in the literature include highly engaged consumers, those requiring external incentives, moderately involved individuals, and consumers with minimal ecological concern. A recent segmentation by Husson et al. (2024) complements this picture by identifying four distinct groups: **Active Greens**, who are highly committed and consistently choose environmentally friendly products even at the expense of price or convenience; **Convenient Greens**, who are ecologically aware but tend to prioritize ease and affordability; **Dormant Greens**, who currently show little environmental concern but may respond positively to appropriate incentives; and **Non-Greens**, who remain disengaged from sustainability issues and base their choices primarily on cost and convenience.

Table 1 summarizes selected consumer typologies discussed in the literature and highlights the diversity of segmentation approaches used in green consumption research. Despite differences in terminology and empirical context, these classifications consistently distinguish between highly engaged consumers, moderately involved individuals, and those largely indifferent or resistant to ecological concerns. This diversity of approaches underscores the need for analytical frameworks that can capture not only differences between consumer groups but also the potential transitions between them.

Based on the EKObaremtr reports from multiple waves conducted between 2020 and 2025 (SW Research, 2020a, 2020b, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025), Polish consumers can be categorized into different ecological segments that reflect their level of environmental engagement and attitudes towards green behaviors. The segmentation, developed using factor analysis and k-means clustering

Table 1: Selected consumer typologies in green consumption literature

Study	Consumer segments	Main characteristics
Roper GfK (1989)	True-blue Greens; Grouzers; Basic Browns	Varying levels of environmental commitment and willingness to adopt eco-friendly behavior
Ottman (1998)	Loyal Green Consumers; Less Devoted Green Consumers; Completely Unwilling to Change	Segmentation based on readiness to adopt green consumption practices
Memery et al. (2005)	Advanced green consumers; Green consumers in transition; Traditional consumers; Apathetic consumers	Differences in commitment to sustainable food purchasing
Banyte et al. (2010)	Black Consumers; Grey Consumers; Greyish Green Consumers; Green Consumers	Segmentation reflecting environmental awareness and actual purchasing behavior
Jaiswal et al. (2021)	Keen Greens; Moderate Greens; Reluctant Greens	Segmentation based on commitment to sustainable purchasing and sensitivity to price and convenience
Husson et al. (2024)	Active Greens; Convenient Greens; Dormant Greens; Non-Greens	Consumer engagement ranging from strong commitment to complete disengagement

on CAWI (Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing) survey data, captures diverse motivations and values behind pro-environmental behaviors. It has evolved over time, reflecting changing societal perceptions of sustainability. In the 2020–2022 studies, consumers were divided into five segments: **Eco-Caring** – concerned about large-scale environmental issues but less engaged in daily eco-friendly behaviors; **Eco-Enthusiasts** – highly committed to sustainability and integrating pro-environmental habits; **Eco-Lost** – lacking ecological habits and showing passivity toward green initiatives; **Eco-Critics** (formerly **Critics of Green Marketing**) – skeptical of green marketing but not opposed to environmental concerns; **Eco-Opportunists** (formerly **Eco-Showoffs**) – advocating for ecological behaviors mainly for self-promotion rather than genuine commitment to sustainability (SW Research, 2020a, 2020b, 2021, 2022). In 2023–2025, the segmentation was revised and stabilized around four key profiles: **Eco-Indifferents**, showing minimal ecological awareness and limited willingness to change consumption habits; **Eco-Enthusiasts**, consistently the most environmentally engaged, combining ideological conviction with concrete daily actions; **Eco-Pretenders**, expressing concern for the environment but rarely translating it into practice; and **Eco-Critics**, the most skeptical and often antagonistic toward sustainability narratives, questioning both the necessity and authenticity of ecological initiatives (SW Research, 2023, 2024, 2025).

The theoretical model of green consumption, based on Bezin (2019), introduces a simplified segmentation of households into **Green Consumers** and **Brown Consumers**. Although highly stylized, the model allows for dynamic transitions driven by socialization – both vertical (within families) and horizontal (via peers and societal norms). The likelihood of children adopting green preferences depends on the cost of pro-environmental upbringing and the prevalence of green consumers in society. When eco-friendly norms are widespread, even children from brown households may shift toward green behaviors. This dynamic view shows how consumer preferences evolve over time due to cultural, economic, and technological factors.

The typologies discussed in the literature suggest that sustainability-oriented consumption should be viewed as a continuum shaped by adaptive behavior and social learning rather than as a set of discrete

categories. Consumer segmentation can therefore be interpreted as representing transient equilibria within an evolving socio-economic environment, where preferences and norms coevolve with technological and institutional change. Movements between more “green” and more “brown” orientations reflect endogenous adjustments to shifting incentives, expectations, and informational contexts. Understanding these dynamics requires an analytical perspective that treats consumer attitudes not as exogenous traits but as elements of an adaptive system – responsive to feedbacks between individual behavior, collective outcomes, and macro-level transformations.

Despite differences in terminology, these typologies consistently point to the existence of distinct stages of environmental engagement among consumers. This observation provides the conceptual basis for the Eco-SEIRN model proposed in this paper, in which consumer segments correspond to dynamic states within the diffusion process of pro-environmental attitudes.

3.2 Proposed Consumer Classification for the Eco-SEIRN Model

Our segmentation of consumers consists of five groups, each representing a different level of ecological awareness and engagement in sustainable consumption: **Susceptible**, **Exposed**, **Involved**, **Responsible Green**, and **Neglectful**. While this typology was developed to meet the structural requirements of our dynamic model, it shows notable conceptual parallels with several well-established segmentations in the literature. In particular, the progression from low to high engagement resembles the structure of the Green Consumer Segmentation proposed by Husson et al. (2024)), while the distinction between intermediate states aligns with refinements seen in Banyte et al. (2010). Moreover, the differentiation of consumer readiness and motivation echoes patterns identified by do Paço et al. (2009) and Verain et al. (2012). Our approach, however, is distinctive in its dynamic nature, explicitly modeling transitions between behavioral states over time to capture the diffusion of pro-environmental attitudes.

In this framework, **Susceptible Consumers** are those with low ecological awareness, who are not yet engaged in green behaviors but may become receptive to sustainability messages. **Exposed Consumers** have been introduced to pro-environmental ideas through media or social influence and are in the early stage of internalizing these ideas, making them more likely to adopt green behaviors. However, they remain highly sensitive to the price of ecological products and are unlikely to choose greener options if these are significantly more expensive than conventional alternatives. **Involved Consumers** actively engage in eco-friendly practices, such as recycling or reducing energy consumption, though their commitment remains moderate and subject to external influences. **Responsible Green Consumers** demonstrate a high level of ecological awareness and a strong commitment to sustainable living, consistently making environmentally conscious choices and actively engaging in a wide range of pro-environmental activities. Finally, **Neglectful Consumers** are indifferent to sustainability issues and resistant to change, either due to skepticism or prioritization of other factors, such as cost and convenience. Our model emphasizes that consumer attitudes are fluid – individuals can shift between these categories over time, driven by changes in knowledge, beliefs, and social reinforcement mechanisms. The segmentation provides the structural basis for modeling the mechanisms behind the diffusion of green consumption attitudes within society.

Our approach deliberately follows a SEIR-type framework, ensuring coherence with established diffusion frameworks while capturing the gradual transition of consumers from resistance to pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors. This design provides a systematic foundation for modeling the dynamics of green consumption across heterogeneous social groups. The consumer categories defined above form the basis for the compartmental structure of the Eco-SEIRN model developed later in this paper.

4 Empirical Background: Pro-Environmental Attitudes in Poland

Before presenting the formal model, it is useful to briefly outline the empirical context of pro-environmental attitudes in Poland, which motivates the calibration and interpretation of the model. Pro-environmental attitudes in Poland have shown notable volatility over the past decade, reflecting both global shifts in public discourse and local socio-economic pressures. In 2015, only 14% of Poles reported being very concerned about climate change (Pew Research Center, 2015). By 2019, however, as many as 73% of respondents in Poland considered climate change a very serious problem (European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment and Kantar, 2020), indicating a substantial increase in the perceived importance of environmental issues. However, recent survey evidence suggests a weakening in the perceived personal relevance of environmental issues. According to the European Commission (2024), the share of respondents in Poland who agreed that environmental issues have a direct effect on their daily life and health declined from 83% in 2019 to 74% in 2024, while the proportion of those expressing disagreement increased from 15% to 25%. This shift points to a growing polarization of attitudes and a reduced perceived immediacy of environmental risks.

A persistent barrier remains the low familiarity with key ecological concepts such as the carbon footprint and greenwashing. In 2020, only about 10–12% of Poles declared awareness of the term “carbon footprint,” compared to roughly 18% in 2025 (SW Research, 2020a, 2025). Recognition of the term “greenwashing” rose more sharply – from 13% in 2020 to 39% in 2025 – yet this growing familiarity has not translated into higher trust. On the contrary, it has contributed to mounting consumer skepticism toward corporate sustainability claims and environmental marketing.

According to the 2025 EKObaremetr report (SW Research, 2025), the structure of ecological personalities has shifted markedly since 2020. The share of *Indifferent* consumers rose from 28% in the first survey wave (2020) to 36% in 2025, while *Enthusiasts* declined from 31% to 26%. The proportion of *Pseudo-Greens* (those displaying selective or inconsistent ecological behaviors) dropped from 26% to 21%, whereas *Critics* – openly skeptical toward ecological narratives – remained relatively stable, fluctuating between 15% and 17%. This configuration indicates a weakening of pro-environmental commitment and an expansion of pragmatic and skeptical attitudes, consistent with broader signs of declining engagement with sustainability themes.

Qualitative findings from the same report reinforce this interpretation. Analysts describe an emerging “ESG crisis,” characterized by diminishing social engagement with sustainability ideals and a reorientation of public priorities toward military security, economic competitiveness, and short-term household needs. Rising living costs have made ecological products and services less accessible, while environmental communication increasingly provokes frustration rather than inspiration. As noted in the report, “many households, preoccupied with rent, energy bills, and food prices, perceive green solutions as secondary or unaffordable” (SW Research, 2025). Even among higher-income consumers, pragmatic considerations dominate: they act sustainably only when it does not require extra effort or cost.

The report also highlights a growing ideological backlash against sustainability discourse, associated with the spread of disinformation on social media. Ecological ideas are at times portrayed as “ecologism,” “leftist ideology,” or “anti-national” constructs imposed by the European Union. Such narratives have intensified in recent years (2023–2025), eroding trust in environmental campaigns and contributing to the stigmatization of ecological behaviors.

Overall, the 2020–2025 data (SW Research, 2020a, 2020b, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025) portray a society in transition – from early optimism and moral engagement toward pragmatic adaptation and selective participation. From a modeling perspective, this heterogeneity provides an empirical foundation

for distinguishing between active promoters, passive adopters, and resistant groups in the diffusion of sustainable attitudes. Although the model is calibrated for the Polish case, its structure is sufficiently general to capture similar polarization processes in other national contexts, provided that comparable segmentation data are available. The empirical patterns described above therefore motivate the structure and calibration of the Eco-SEIRN model introduced in the following section.

5 Eco-SEIRN Model

The Eco-SEIRN model presented in this study is inspired by the classical SEIR epidemiological framework (see, e.g., Kermack and McKendrick, 1927; Hethcote, 2000; Cuesta-Herrera et al., 2022), commonly used to describe the spread of infectious diseases. In this modeling approach, a population is divided into compartments representing different behavioral states, and transitions between these states are described using a system of differential equations. Adapting the SEIR framework to consumer behavior allows us to capture the evolving nature of ecological awareness and the gradual adoption of sustainable consumption practices. The compartments used in the model correspond to the consumer categories discussed in the previous section, reflecting different levels of ecological awareness and engagement.

In the original SEIR model, the population is represented as being distributed across four compartments: Susceptible, Exposed, Infected, and Recovered. Similarly, the Eco-SEIRN model is based on five consumer groups with varying levels of ecological awareness: Susceptible Consumers, Exposed Consumers, Involved Consumers, Responsible Green Consumers, and Neglectful Consumers. The transitions between these groups are influenced by factors such as media intensity and peer interactions, which reflects the spread of ecological behaviors and the influence of both pro-ecological and neglectful attitudes within the population. The equations and parameters defined in the Eco-SEIRN model aim to quantitatively describe how consumers evolve across different stages of ecological awareness, with a particular focus on the role of media in accelerating the transition towards responsible consumption patterns.

To make the behavioral logic of the model explicit, each transition parameter is linked to a distinct mechanism discussed in the literature. The parameter β_I captures pro-environmental peer influence, that is, the social contagion through which contact with eco-aware consumers increases the probability that susceptible individuals become exposed to ecological ideas. This interpretation is consistent with diffusion-of-innovations theory and complex contagion models, which emphasize that social influence and repeated exposure are central to the spread of new attitudes and practices (Granovetter, 1978; Rogers, 2003; Centola and Macy, 2007). By contrast, β_N represents counter-normative pressure: contact with neglectful consumers reinforces indifferent or convenience-oriented routines and shifts susceptible individuals away from ecological engagement.

The parameters σ_1 and σ_2 govern the stability of intermediate awareness. The coefficient σ_1 represents behavioral activation, namely the transition from ecological awareness to actual involvement in pro-environmental practices. In behavioral terms, it reflects the step from favorable attitudes to action emphasized in the Theory of Planned Behavior and related work on pro-environmental intentions (Ajzen, 1985; Bamberg and Möser, 2007). In turn, σ_2 captures demobilization under neglectful influence: exposed consumers may lose weakly internalized ecological awareness and return to a more passive – susceptible – state when surrounded by indifferent or skeptical social norms. The parameters γ_r and γ_i describe reinforcement and partial erosion of commitment within the already engaged population. They represent, respectively, the consolidation of ecological responsibility and the weakening of that commitment, in line with research on norm internalization, group identity, and the attitude-behavior gap (Stern et al., 1999; Fielding et al., 2008; Wyss et al., 2022).

Finally, media-related parameters play two analytically distinct roles in the model. The dynamic variable $M(t)$, together with r , r_0 , M_0 , and m , describes the activation, decay, baseline salience, and saturation of ecological communication. By contrast, α does not represent media influence in general; rather, it measures the specific capacity of media exposure, combined with the visible presence of eco-aware consumers, to reduce resistance among neglectful individuals and move them into a more receptive state. This distinction is important for interpreting the model consistently: media salience affects several transitions through $M(t)$, whereas α refers specifically to the resistance-breaking conversion of the neglectful group (Bass, 1969; Misra et al., 2018).

5.1 The Model

The five consumer groups considered in the Eco-SEIRN model are defined as:

$S(t)$ — Susceptible Consumers (Brown / Non-ecological Consumers): individuals with minimal ecological awareness;

$E(t)$ — Exposed Consumers (Grey / Average Consumers): individuals beginning to be engaged with ecological ideas but not yet involved;

$I(t)$ — Involved Consumers (Greyish Green / Environmentally Friendly Consumers): individuals actively participating in eco-friendly behaviors;

$R(t)$ — Responsible Green Consumers (Green / Ecological Consumers): highly conscious and committed consumers adopting sustainable consumption practices;

$NE(t)$ — Neglectful Consumers (Black Consumers): individuals indifferent to ecological concerns.

The model assumes a constant total population N , such that:

$$N = S(t) + E(t) + I(t) + R(t) + NE(t). \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, media influence plays an important role in the Eco-SEIRN model, represented by $M(t)$, which denotes the intensity of media-driven promotion of ecological behaviors through various media channels, including social media (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Structure and transition mechanisms in the Eco-SEIRN model of pro-environmental attitude dynamics. The figure presents the flows between five consumer groups (from left to right: Neglectful, Susceptible, Exposed, Involved, and Responsible Green) along with transition rates driven by peer effects and media-related mechanisms, including $M(t)$.

The Eco-SEIRN dynamic system is governed by a set of differential equations that describe how consumer groups evolve over time under the joint influence of peer interactions and media-driven ecological awareness:

$$\begin{aligned}
S'(t) = & -\beta_I \cdot \frac{E(t) + I(t) + R(t)}{N} \cdot \frac{M(t)}{m + M(t)} \cdot S(t) \\
& - \beta_N \cdot \frac{NE(t)}{N} \cdot S(t) \\
& + \sigma_2 \cdot \frac{NE(t)}{N} \cdot E(t) \\
& + \alpha \cdot \frac{M(t)}{m + M(t)} \cdot \frac{E(t) + I(t) + R(t)}{N} \cdot NE(t)
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E'(t) = & \beta_I \cdot \frac{E(t) + I(t) + R(t)}{N} \cdot \frac{M(t)}{m + M(t)} \cdot S(t) \\
& - \sigma_1 \cdot \frac{M(t)}{m + M(t)} \cdot \frac{I(t) + R(t)}{N} \cdot E(t) \\
& - \sigma_2 \cdot \frac{NE(t)}{N} \cdot E(t)
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$$I'(t) = \sigma_1 \cdot \frac{M(t)}{m + M(t)} \cdot \frac{I(t) + R(t)}{N} \cdot E(t) - \gamma_r I(t) + \gamma_i R(t) \tag{4}$$

$$R'(t) = -\gamma_i R(t) + \gamma_r I(t) \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
NE'(t) = & \beta_N \cdot \frac{NE(t)}{N} \cdot S(t) \\
& - \alpha \cdot \frac{M(t)}{m + M(t)} \cdot \frac{E(t) + I(t) + R(t)}{N} \cdot NE(t)
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$$M'(t) = r \cdot \frac{NE(t) + S(t)}{N} - r_0 \cdot (M(t) - M_0) \tag{7}$$

The transitions between the groups are governed by the interaction of interpersonal influence and media salience. Susceptible consumers ($S(t)$) become exposed ($E(t)$) when they encounter eco-aware consumers and when ecological messages are sufficiently visible in the media. This mechanism is captured by the parameter β_I and amplified by the saturation term $\frac{M(t)}{m+M(t)}$. In contrast, contact with neglectful consumers shifts susceptible individuals toward the neglectful state ($NE(t)$) at rate β_N , reflecting the stabilizing force of indifferent or skeptical social norms.

Exposed consumers occupy an intermediate state. They may progress to active involvement ($I(t)$) through reinforcement from already engaged consumers and media salience, as described by σ_1 , or they may lose this weakly internalized awareness and return to the susceptible state under neglectful influence, as described by σ_2 . Once consumers become involved, they may further strengthen their ecological commitment and transition to the Responsible Green group ($R(t)$) at rate γ_r , while γ_i captures partial erosion of commitment from $R(t)$ back to $I(t)$. Finally, neglectful consumers do not move directly into the exposed state in the baseline specification. Instead, the parameter α captures a narrower mechanism:

under sufficiently strong media salience and visible presence of eco-aware groups, some neglectful consumers become susceptible again, that is, more open to ecological influence. This formulation separates general media salience, represented by $M(t)$, from the specific resistance-breaking conversion of the neglectful group, represented by α . To clarify the theoretical meaning of the model parameters, Table 2 links each coefficient not only to its mathematical role in the system but also to the behavioral mechanism it is intended to capture.

In behavioral terms, the Eco-SEIRN model combines three interconnected layers of influence. First, β_I and β_N represent opposing forms of social pressure: pro-environmental contagion generated by eco-aware consumers and counter-normative reinforcement generated by neglectful consumers. This reflects the idea, well established in diffusion theory, that behavioral change depends not only on exposure to innovation but also on the local strength of competing norms (Granovetter, 1978; Rogers, 2003; Centola and Macy, 2007).

Second, σ_1 and σ_2 determine whether intermediate awareness becomes stabilized or dissipates. The parameter σ_1 captures activation into practice, that is, the transformation of ecological awareness into observable involvement in pro-environmental behaviors. This interpretation is consistent with the behavioral literature showing that favorable attitudes do not automatically translate into action unless they are reinforced by perceived feasibility, social approval, and repeated cues (Ajzen, 1985; Bamberg and Möser, 2007). By contrast, σ_2 captures demobilization under neglectful influence: exposed consumers may lose weakly internalized ecological salience before it becomes durable practice.

Third, γ_r and γ_i govern reinforcement and partial erosion within the already engaged population. They reflect the idea that ecological commitment is not binary but can strengthen or weaken over time depending on social reinforcement, identity processes, and the persistence of supportive norms (Stern et al., 1999; Fielding et al., 2008; Wyss et al., 2022). Media influence enters the model through two distinct channels. The variable $M(t)$ and the parameters r , r_0 , M_0 , and m describe the endogenous dynamics of ecological communication, including activation, decay, baseline salience, and saturation. The parameter α , in turn, has a narrower role: it measures the capacity of media exposure, combined with the visible presence of eco-aware consumers, to reduce resistance among neglectful individuals and move them back into a susceptible, and therefore more receptive state. This distinction makes the logic of the model more transparent and prevents interpreting α as a general media-effect parameter.

An example of how media intensity $M(t)$ can be effectively utilized is the mobile application described by Asikis et al. (2021). This tool supports sustainable consumption by providing transparent information about the environmental impact of products, enhancing consumer awareness and facilitating behavioral shifts. Such technologies align with the assumptions underlying $M(t)$ in the Eco-SEIRN model and illustrate how digital tools can support transitions across consumer groups by reinforcing the mechanisms of media influence and informational exposure.

In summary, the Eco-SEIRN model integrates both intergroup influence and media intensity as crucial mechanisms driving consumer transitions between different levels of ecological awareness. The interplay of these parameters enables the model to capture both the positive effects of widespread eco-awareness and the challenges posed by neglectful behavior and the saturation effects in media-driven communication.

5.2 Tipping Point and Early-Stage Dynamics in the Eco-SEIRN Model

In order to better understand the emergence and spread of ecological attitudes, we analyzed the early-stage dynamics of the proposed Eco-SEIRN model. In particular, we focused on identifying the *tipping point* - the critical threshold at which ecological awareness begins to spread throughout the population (i.e., when the growth rate of the Exposed group becomes positive).

We considered a near-initial state in which the vast majority of individuals belong to the Susceptible

Table 2: Parameters of the Eco-SEIRN model and their interpretation

Symbol	Parameter	Description
N	Total population size	Constant total number of consumers in the system, composed of all five behavioral groups: Susceptible, Exposed, Involved, Responsible Green, and Neglectful.
$M(t)$	Media intensity	Dynamic variable representing the intensity of ecological promotion through various media channels (including social media and campaigns). Drives awareness transitions between groups.
m	Media saturation threshold	Half-saturation constant in the term $\frac{M}{m+M}$, representing diminishing marginal returns to additional media intensity.
r	Media activation rate	Rate at which media salience increases in response to a higher share of Susceptible and Neglectful consumers in the population.
r_0	Media decay rate	Rate at which media salience returns toward its baseline level as campaign pressure weakens over time.
M_0	Baseline media salience	Background level of ecological communication in the absence of additional activation.
β_I	Eco-aware peer influence rate	Rate at which contact with eco-aware consumers (E , I , R) moves Susceptible individuals into the Exposed state. It captures interpersonal ecological contagion and social reinforcement.
β_N	Neglectful normative pressure rate	Rate at which Neglectful Consumers shift Susceptible individuals toward the Neglectful state by reinforcing indifferent, skeptical, or convenience-oriented norms.
σ_1	Behavioral activation rate	Transition rate from Exposed (E) to Involved (I), driven by the joint influence of already engaged consumers (I , R) and media salience. It represents the translation of awareness into actual pro-environmental practice.
σ_2	Demobilization under neglectful influence	Rate at which Exposed consumers (E) lose weakly internalized ecological awareness and return to the Susceptible state after contact with Neglectful Consumers.
γ_r	Commitment reinforcement rate	Transition rate from Involved (I) to Responsible Green (R), reflecting the consolidation of ecological commitment and the stabilization of sustainable practices.
γ_i	Commitment erosion rate	Transition rate from Responsible Green (R) back to Involved (I), reflecting partial weakening of commitment rather than complete abandonment of pro-environmental behavior.
α	Resistance-breaking conversion rate	Rate at which Neglectful Consumers become Susceptible again when media salience and the visible presence of eco-aware groups jointly reduce resistance to ecological messages.

group ($S \approx N$), while the numbers of Exposed (E), Involved (I), Responsible Green (R), and Neglectful (NE) consumers remain initially negligible. Under this approximation, the growth rate of the Exposed group becomes the key indicator of whether ecological attitudes will propagate or diminish.

By linearizing the differential equation (3) governing the dynamics of the Exposed group, we derived

the following condition:

$$\frac{E'(t)}{E} \approx \frac{M \cdot \beta_I}{M + m} \quad (8)$$

This expression acts as an *ecological reproduction index*, capturing the interplay between the influence of media (M), the effectiveness of ecological peer influence (β_I), and the saturation threshold (m). A tipping point is reached when the expression exceeds a critical threshold required to compensate for system resistance (e.g., influence from the Neglectful group or low media exposure). Below this threshold, ecological behavior remains marginal; above it, a cascade toward ecological awareness may unfold.

Importantly, the value of $\frac{M \cdot \beta_I}{M + m}$ is always positive for $M > 0$, but the *magnitude* must be sufficient to overcome dissipative forces such as disengagement (σ_2) or social resistance from Neglectful Consumers, which are omitted in the initial approximation but become relevant beyond the early stage. Thus, the model predicts the existence of a *critical media intensity*, M_{critical} , beyond which ecological attitudes begin to spread sustainably.

This analytical insight provides a foundation for further simulations exploring how different combinations of parameters and initial conditions may lead to vastly different long-term outcomes – ranging from ecological stagnation to rapid societal transformation. It also reinforces the pivotal role of media campaigns and group-to-group influence in catalyzing ecological transitions.

5.3 Stationary States in the Eco-SEIRN Model

The stationary state (also referred to as a steady state or equilibrium) in the Eco-SEIRN model refers to a condition in which the proportions of the consumer groups (S, E, I, R, NE) and the level of media exposure M related to pro-environmental behaviors remain constant over time. This implies that the net flows between groups are balanced and that media influence has reached a steady level.

Formally, a stationary state is described by the vector $(S^*, E^*, I^*, R^*, NE^*, M^*)$, for which the right-hand sides of equations (2)–(7) are equal to zero. By solving the system of these equations with the right-hand sides set to zero, we analytically derive expressions characterizing exactly four stationary states of the Eco-SEIRN model (see Table 3). Stationary state P_1 represents a scenario of full societal engagement in pro-environmental actions - where all consumers belong to either the Involved or Responsible groups. This reflects the effectiveness of information campaigns and a sustained transformation of public attitudes. In this state, the level of media exposure remains at its baseline value. State P_2 corresponds to a population entirely unaware of environmental issues. In contrast, state P_3 describes a population that is aware of ecological concerns, yet consumers engage in environmentally friendly behaviors only to a limited extent. State P_4 , on the other hand, is characterized by a complete lack of interest in ecological topics - all consumers belong to the Neglectful group, and despite the presence of information campaigns, their attitudes remain unchanged.

variable	stationary state			
	P1	P2	P3	P4
Susceptible S^*	0	N	0	0
Exposed E^*	0	0	N	0
Involved I^*	$\frac{\gamma_i N}{\gamma_i + \gamma_r}$	0	0	0
Responsible Green R^*	$\frac{\gamma_r N}{\gamma_i + \gamma_r}$	0	0	0
Neglectful NE^*	0	0	0	N
Media M^*	M_0	$\frac{r}{r_0} + M_0$	M_0	$\frac{r}{r_0} + M_0$

Table 3: Stationary States in the Eco-SEIRN Model

In the subsequent analysis, we evaluated the stability of the identified stationary states (equilibria) by examining whether the model variables converge toward them over time. Based on standard stability analysis for stationary states in autonomous systems of nonlinear differential equations, we demonstrated that state P_2 is unstable, whereas the remaining three states exhibit stability conditional on the initial distribution of consumer groups.

Saying that state P_2 is unstable means that a situation, in which the entire population remains unaware of environmental issues, cannot persist as a stable outcome of the system dynamics. Even a small stimulus – such as a minor media campaign, peer influence, or grassroots initiative – can trigger change and shift the system toward increased ecological awareness. In contrast, the remaining three states (P_1 , P_3 , P_4) exhibit stability that depends on initial conditions and parameter values, which makes them sensitive to external disturbances. Although they are not easily disrupted, sufficiently strong interventions (e.g., intensive policies or information shocks) can move the system toward a different stationary state. From an economic perspective, this implies that:

- society may remain stuck in a low-engagement state (P_3), where awareness does not translate into action, or in a state of apathy (P_4), characterized by a lack of responsiveness to environmental concerns;
- full engagement (P_1) is feasible but requires sufficiently strong and persistent pro-environmental influence (e.g., through media intensity and peer effects) to remain stable;
- each of these outcomes is path-dependent, meaning that once the system follows a particular trajectory, it is hard to reverse it without substantial intervention.

Moreover, the analytical inspection of the model equations suggests that states P_3 and P_4 are dynamically unstable whenever the initial state includes any pro-environmentally engaged consumers. This results from the fact that individuals in the Involved (I) and Responsible Green (R) groups do not transition to less engaged categories (i.e., E , S , or NE). Therefore, stability of these states is only possible when $I = R = 0$, a condition which we do not further consider in this article. If the initial state of the population includes even a small number of pro-environmentally engaged consumers (belonging to the Involved or Responsible Green groups), then the system cannot remain in either state P_3 (limited engagement) or P_4 (complete neglect). In economic terms, this leads to the following conclusions:

- the presence of even a small minority of green-engaged consumers can have a disproportionate influence on the rest of society, initiating a dynamic process of attitude change;
- these individuals act as catalysts for social transformation, and since the model assumes they do not revert to less engaged states, their influence accumulates over time;
- as a result, stagnation scenarios (P_3 and P_4) are only possible in the complete absence of committed green consumers, which is considered unrealistic and thus not further explored in the analysis.

In the Appendix, we formally establish the stability of the stationary state P_1 using LaSalle's Invariance Principle. The next section presents the numerical analysis of the model.

6 Numerical Analysis of Eco-Attitude Spread

Building upon the theoretical framework developed in the previous section, this part of the study presents a numerical simulation of the system defined by equations (2)–(7), implemented in Python. The simulations aim to examine the stability of the stationary state P_1 , to analyze the influence of media activity on the evolution of the model variables, and to identify the conditions under which full societal engagement in pro-environmental behavior can be sustained. This approach also allows us to assess how media intensity $M(t)$ affects the system's convergence toward the steady state and whether it can

reinforce or destabilize the socially desirable equilibrium.

6.1 Model Parameter Calibration

The model parameters were calibrated using data from six EKObarometer reports for the period 2020–2024 (SW Research (2020a, 2020b, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024)). While earlier reports use a slightly different classification, the 2023 and 2024 EKObarometer reports distinguish four consumer categories – Eco-Lost, Eco-Concerned, Eco-Enthusiasts, and Eco-Critics. For calibration purposes, these categories were mapped onto the model structure as follows: Eco-Lost \rightarrow Susceptible (S), Eco-Concerned \rightarrow Exposed (E), and Eco-Critics \rightarrow Neglectful (NE). To meet the model’s requirement for five distinct compartments, the Eco-Enthusiasts category was divided into two equally sized groups: Involved (I) and Responsible Green (R), which constitutes a simplifying assumption. Additionally, the variable M , representing the intensity of promotional and advertising activities, was calibrated.

The Eco-SEIRN model consists of six nonlinear differential equations with eleven parameters describing the dynamics of transitions between consumer groups and media-driven processes. The following parameters are considered: β_I , β_N , σ_1 , σ_2 , γ_r , γ_i , α , r , r_0 , m , and M_0 . All parameters were constrained to lie within the interval $[0, 0.10]$, reflecting the assumption that transition rates in social and behavioral dynamics remain relatively low per unit of time. Values within this interval can be interpreted as plausible upper bounds of transition intensities in social diffusion processes. For instance, a value of 0.05 corresponds to a scenario in which up to 5% of a given group may transition to another state within a single time unit under intensified social influence. Numerous social diffusion and epidemiological models adopt parameters of comparable magnitude to capture the gradual, rather than instantaneous, nature of behavioral transitions (Centola and Macy, 2007; Bikhchandani et al., 1992). Constraining the parameter space in this way also helps ensure numerical stability and interpretability while allowing the optimization routine to converge toward empirically plausible stationary states.

The parameter m is defined as the saturation point of the system, that is, the value of $M(t)$ at which the effectiveness of the campaign reaches 50% of its maximum level. In the model, the value $m = 10/365$ is adopted, corresponding to approximately ten significant media campaign waves per year, expressed in daily units. This calibration reflects a moderate frequency of exposure, consistent with typical national environmental awareness campaigns reported in EKObarometer data. Conceptually, m acts as a saturation constant analogous to the half-activation point in logistic response functions, marking the intensity level at which marginal returns to additional media effort begin to diminish. This specification implies that even a moderate level of media exposure is sufficient to achieve half of the potential impact on consumer attitudes.

The total number of consumers in the population remains constant and is set to $N = 100$. This assumption simplifies the model and enables a direct interpretation of results in terms of the percentage share of each consumer group. In the present version of the model, the focus is on the mechanisms of transitions between attitudes within a closed community, which is sufficient to capture the main patterns of ecological awareness dynamics. In future research, we intend to extend the model by incorporating inflow and outflow mechanisms related to demographic change. These would capture the entry of new generations of consumers – potentially more environmentally aware – into the system, as well as the gradual exit of older cohorts. Accounting for such population turnover would allow for a more realistic representation of long-term social and cultural dynamics.

The parameter estimation was conducted using an evolutionary algorithm implemented in the `scipy.optimize.differential_evolution` function from the SciPy library in Python. This algorithm is particularly well suited to nonlinear objective functions that exhibit multiple local minima. The method builds on the approach introduced by Storn and Price (1997), who proposed differential evolution

as a robust global optimization technique suitable for continuous, nonlinear, and non-differentiable spaces. Its implementation in the SciPy library facilitates reproducibility and computational efficiency in parameter fitting for complex dynamic models.

The objective of the optimization process was to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) between the values generated by the model and the empirical data for the period 2020 to 2024. This time frame corresponds to the available data from six consecutive waves of the EKObareometr survey (SW Research (2020a, 2020b, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024)). The objective function is defined as follows:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left(\sum_{x \in \{S, E, I, R, NE\}} (x_{\text{model}}(t) - x_{\text{data}}(t))^2 \right),$$

where $n = 6$ is the number of observations, and $x_{\text{model}}(t)$ and $x_{\text{data}}(t)$ denote, respectively, the values of the variables generated by the model and observed in the empirical data. During the calibration process, two constraints were imposed:

- the state variables satisfy the population constraint:

$$S(t) + E(t) + I(t) + R(t) + NE(t) = N = 100;$$

- the media intensity satisfies:

$$M(0) = 10, \quad M(t) \geq 0.$$

The estimated parameter values are reported in Table 4.

parameter	value	parameter	value
β_I	0.01175	γ_r	0.05635
β_N	0.07083	γ_i	0.04575
σ_1	0.00068	α	0.04150
σ_2	0.07201	r	0.02393
r_0	0.06188		

Table 4: Estimated parameters of the Eco-SEIRN Model

The fitted model achieved a total mean squared error of:

$$\text{MSE}_{\text{global}} = 8.92.$$

This value indicates a reasonable level of correspondence between the simulated trajectories and the observed trends in consumer group shares, especially given the limited number of data points and the aggregate nature of the survey categories. The magnitude of the error should be interpreted in the context of data uncertainty and limited resolution, as well as the complexity and interdependence of the model parameters.

Prior to conducting the simulations, the initial values of the model variables appearing in equations (2)–(7) were specified. The total population was normalized to $N = 100$, which allows the model variables to be interpreted as percentage shares of consumer groups. The initial state corresponds to the beginning of 2024, with the following values: $S(0) = 26$, $E(0) = 28$, $I(0) = 15.5$, $R(0) = 15.5$, and $NE(0) = 15$. The initial level of media activity was set exogenously at $M(0) = 10$, representing a moderate baseline level of promotional exposure. This value reflects the typical intensity of environmental communication observed in the EKObareometr data.

Among the stationary states identified in the model, P_1 represents the only dynamically stable

long-term outcome under non-zero engagement and complete transition of the population into environmentally responsible groups. Therefore, the subsequent analysis focuses on this equilibrium. The stationary state P_1 was computed using the parameter values reported in Table 4 and the characterization of stationary states provided in Table 3. The values of the variables at the stationary state are summarized in Table 5, together with their initial values.

Variable	Initial value	Stationary state P_1
Susceptible S	26	0
Exposed E	28	0
Involved I	15.5	44.81
Responsible Green R	15.5	55.19
Neglectful NE	15	0
Media M	10	10

Table 5: Initial values and stationary state P_1 of the model variables

6.2 Simulation Results

Because the system of equations (2)–(7) is nonlinear, its dynamics were investigated using numerical simulations. The simulations were performed using the Runge–Kutta–Fehlberg method implemented in Python¹. The time unit is one day. Thus, 10 950 time steps correspond to a 30-year simulation horizon. This period was selected as sufficiently long to capture the stabilization of long-term consumer behavior patterns.

For clarity of interpretation, the time axis in the simulation figures was rescaled to yearly units, covering the period 2024–2064. The daily time scale is consistent with the calibration of transition parameters between consumer groups. In particular, the parameter values capture annual structural changes in the population while the model is formulated at a daily resolution. The simulation results are presented in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Simulated trajectories of S, E, I, R, NE (2024–2064)

The primary objective of the simulations is to analyze the stability of the stationary state P_1 and to examine how varying levels of media intensity influence the evolution of consumer groups. The results for the period 2024–2064 reveal a complex dynamic pattern of transitions between consumer groups, accompanied by changes in the intensity of media influence.

In the initial phase, the size of the Exposed Consumers group (E) declines, as does the Susceptible group (S), following a short-lived increase in the initial period. At the same time, the number of Neglectful Consumers (NE) increases. These changes occur without significant fluctuations in the shares of the Involved (I) and Responsible Green (R) groups. This pattern results from the relatively

¹An interactive application with the studied model is available at: <https://ecoseirn5model.streamlit.app/>

high values of parameters β_N and σ_2 compared to β_I and σ_1 (see Table 4), implying that the dominant transition pathway in the early stage follows the sequence:

$$E \rightarrow S \rightarrow NE,$$

which represents a two-step process in which consumers first become susceptible and subsequently drift toward indifference. This mechanism accounts for the decline in the sizes of groups E and S and the concurrent increase in NE . In subsequent phases, media influence intensifies, driven by the growth of the NE group and the persistent presence of the S group. As a result, the direction of flows shifts: initially, a marked increase in the number of Exposed Consumers (E) is observed, accompanied by a decline in S and NE , followed by a gradual reallocation of the population toward the most environmentally engaged groups – Involved (I) and Responsible Green (R) – together with a reduction in the size of E .

The trajectories of groups I and R are highly similar, exhibiting nearly parallel and steady growth throughout the simulation horizon (except for a slight initial decline in I). This convergence stems from the calibration assumptions, namely the initial parity in group sizes and the similarity of transition parameters γ_i and γ_r . The media intensity variable (M) increases sharply in the early stage of the simulation and subsequently stabilizes before gradually declining toward its baseline steady state level. This behavior arises from the model structure, in which media activity is positively correlated with the sizes of the Susceptible (S) and Neglectful (NE) groups, while being constrained by a self-regulating adjustment toward M_0 . The peak in media intensity occurs when the population still contains a substantial proportion of susceptible and neglectful consumers. As the shares of S and NE approach zero, media activity gradually declines toward its baseline steady state level.

Figure 3: Simulated trajectory of media intensity $M(t)$ (2024–2064)

In the final phase, the trajectories converge to the steady state P_1 (see Table 5), in which the entire population belongs to pro-environmental groups. The final distribution between Involved consumers (I) and Responsible Green consumers (R) depends on the relative magnitudes of parameters γ_i and γ_r . Importantly, the simulation results are consistent with the analytical finding of local asymptotic stability of the stationary state P_1 .

Overall, the findings indicate that media act as a critical feedback mechanism capable of both reinforcing and temporarily attenuating pro-environmental transformation processes. The effectiveness of pro-environmental communication therefore depends not only on its intensity but also on the evolving structural composition of the consumer population. This highlights the importance of sustained and adaptive media strategies in fostering long-term behavioral change.

6.3 Model Sensitivity to Resistance-Breaking Conversion and Campaign Intensity

Impact of Resistance-Breaking Media Conversion (α) on Behavioral Transitions

The parameter α does not capture media effectiveness in general. Rather, it represents the specific

capacity of media exposure, combined with the visible presence of eco-aware consumers, to reduce resistance among Neglectful Consumers (NE) and move them into the Susceptible state (S), that is, into a more receptive and reachable position. Higher values of α therefore correspond to communication that is more credible, less polarizing, better targeted to resistant audiences, and more capable of weakening skepticism or disengagement. Lower values of α indicate that ecological messages remain present but fail to overcome resistance in the neglectful segment. Figure 4 illustrates how changes in α affect the dynamics of the Neglectful group.

Figure 4: Share of Neglectful Consumers ($NE(t)$) under different values of the resistance-breaking conversion parameter α

A comparison of the dynamics of Neglectful Consumers population (NE) across different values of α shows that this parameter strongly affects the persistence of resistant consumers in the system. Since α governs the resistance-breaking conversion from the Neglectful state to the Susceptible state, higher values of α do not correspond to stronger media influence in general. Rather, they indicate that existing communication is more successful in softening skepticism and making neglectful consumers reachable again.

The analysis shows that even a marginal increase in α leads to a faster decline in the proportion of Neglectful Consumers, especially in the later stages of the simulation. In the scenario with the lowest value of α , the share of neglectful consumers remains relatively high for a prolonged period, indicating that ecological communication is insufficient to overcome resistance in that segment. By contrast, even a marginal increase in α produces a clearly faster reduction in the NE group. In the scenario with the highest value of α , the neglectful segment declines to zero much earlier, suggesting that relatively small improvements in credibility, framing, or audience-specific targeting may substantially accelerate long-run behavioral change.

These findings have important practical implications. They suggest that communication policy should focus not only on expanding ecological messaging but also on improving its capacity to reduce resistance among skeptical or disengaged audiences. In practical terms, this involves using more credible messengers, less moralizing and less polarizing framing, and better tailoring of messages to groups that are initially indifferent or hostile to sustainability narratives. Even relatively small improvements in this resistance-breaking capacity may substantially accelerate the decline of neglectful attitudes over time.

Impact of Media Intensity (r) on Attitude Dynamics

In the model, the parameter r determines the rate at which media activity increases in response to awareness-related needs. It reflects how strongly pro-environmental communication ($M(t)$) expands in response to the presence of Neglectful Consumers (NE) and Susceptible Consumers (S) in the population. Figure 5 illustrates the effect of varying r on the dynamics of the model variables.

Figure 5: Share of Neglectful Consumers ($NE(t)$) under different values of the parameter r

The results indicate that higher values of r significantly affect the trajectory of Neglectful Consumers (NE). Although larger values of r do not produce an immediate decline in the number of Neglectful Consumers, they substantially limit the growth rate of this group, lower its peak value, and accelerate its convergence to zero. For larger r , the NE curve reaches its maximum at a lower level, followed by a gradual decline toward zero. However, the post-peak rate of decline appears to be largely insensitive to the value of r .

Compared to the effects of increasing the effectiveness of media messaging (parameter α), achieving a noticeable impact on the NE variable through an increase in media campaign intensity (parameter r) requires a substantially larger, several-fold increase in its value. This pattern is illustrated by the set of curves: the blue line corresponds to $r = 0.001$, the green line to the baseline value $r = 0.005$, the yellow line to nearly twice the baseline ($r = 0.009$), the red line to three times the baseline ($r = 0.015$), and the violet line to six times the baseline ($r = 0.03$). This indicates that achieving a significant impact through media activity alone, by increasing its intensity, requires substantial amplification.

Conversely, reducing media intensity yields a comparatively moderate effect. Even a fivefold decrease in r relative to the baseline (blue curve, $r = 0.001$) does not fundamentally alter the trajectory of $NE(t)$. The timing of the peak and the subsequent decline remain broadly comparable to the baseline case ($r = 0.005$). This indicates that, under conditions of sufficiently high media effectiveness (i.e., sufficiently large α), the system exhibits relative robustness to reductions in campaign intensity. In other words, when message quality or persuasive strength is high, lower intensity does not substantially weaken behavioral transformation dynamics.

Interaction Between Resistance-Breaking Conversion (α) and Campaign Intensity (r)

We examine the combined effect of resistance-breaking conversion (α) and campaign intensity (r) to assess how their interaction shapes the dynamics of Neglectful Consumers ($NE(t)$). The parameter α governs the ability of ecological communication to reduce resistance among Neglectful Consumers, whereas r

determines the rate at which ecological communication is activated and sustained in the population. The simulations therefore allow us to distinguish between communication quality directed at resistant audiences and communication volume or intensity.

As demonstrated by the simulation results in Figure 6, an increase in α substantially alters the dynamics of Neglectful Consumers population ($NE(t)$). Even a modest rise in α leads to a faster convergence of $NE(t)$ toward zero and a lower peak level during the initial phase of the simulation. At the same time, as α increases, the marginal effect of further changes in r becomes weaker. This indicates that once communication becomes sufficiently effective at reducing resistance in the neglectful segment, additional increases in campaign intensity produce diminishing returns.

Figure 6: Effect of campaign intensity (r) on the dynamics of Neglectful Consumers ($NE(t)$) under different levels of resistance-breaking conversion (α)

A key finding is the nonlinear interdependence between communication quality and communication intensity. The results suggest that improving the ability of messages to reduce skepticism and disengagement among Neglectful Consumers generates stronger and more persistent effects than increasing communication intensity alone. When α is low, even intensive campaigns fail to induce substantial change because exposure is not converted into receptivity. Conversely, once α exceeds a certain threshold, increases in r primarily accelerate an already effective process rather than fundamentally altering its direction.

6.4 Summary of Simulation Results

The simulation results highlight the central role of media-related parameters in shaping the trajectory of ecological awareness within the population. However, the functions of α and r are structurally distinct. The parameter r governs the activation of ecological communication, whereas α captures its ability to reduce resistance among Neglectful Consumers and move them into a more reachable state. This distinction is crucial for a consistent interpretation of the model. The identified nonlinear relationship between these parameters indicates that improving the resistance-breaking quality of communication (higher α) generates substantially greater systemic impact than increasing the intensity of communication alone (higher r).

Media influence acts as a key accelerator of behavioral diffusion, but it does not alter the ultimate stationary state of the system. The long-term distribution of consumer groups depends primarily on structural parameters such as γ_r and γ_i , which govern internal reinforcement and partial erosion between Involved and Responsible Consumers. Media campaigns can accelerate transitions toward pro-environmental engagement, but the resulting equilibrium is sustained by social imitation and the internalization of ecological norms rather than by continuous external intervention.

From a systemic perspective, we establish the existence and local asymptotic stability of the steady state P_1 , representing a socially desirable configuration in which pro-environmental attitudes are self-reinforcing and resilient to moderate shocks. Economically, this stationary state corresponds to a shift in preferences stabilized by endogenous social mechanisms rather than by continuous external intervention. While the current specification treats media influence as an endogenous process through $M(t)$, future extensions may incorporate exogenous intervention terms – such as policy-triggered campaign bursts – to capture deliberate policy shocks and their transient macro-behavioral effects.

7 Conclusions, Implications, Limitations, and Future Research

This study develops an Eco-SEIRN framework to examine how pro-environmental consumer attitudes diffuse within a population under the joint influence of interpersonal interactions and media-mediated salience. By adapting the logic of compartmental diffusion models to consumer behavior, the paper provides a stylized yet analytically tractable representation of how ecological awareness may emerge, stabilize, or fail to spread across heterogeneous social groups. The results show that transitions toward stronger ecological engagement depend not only on exposure to pro-environmental messages, but also on the interaction between social reinforcement, resistance, and the persistence of already engaged consumers.

The desirable steady state identified in the model should be interpreted as a stylized long-run attractor under the assumptions of the framework, rather than as a direct forecast of real-world societal convergence. In this sense, the Eco-SEIRN model does not imply that sustainability transitions in consumption are linear or inevitable. Instead, it highlights a specific mechanism through which pro-environmental orientations may become self-reinforcing, namely the interaction between social reinforcement, the reduction of resistance, and the visible presence of already engaged groups.

Theoretical implications. The paper makes three main theoretical contributions. First, it shows that pro-environmental diffusion should not be treated as a binary shift between “green” and “non-green” consumers. Instead, the Eco-SEIRN framework distinguishes between low awareness, early exposure, active involvement, stabilized ecological responsibility, and neglectful resistance. This allows sustainable consumption to be represented as a multi-stage process in which awareness, activation, and reinforcement are analytically distinct.

Second, the model formalizes the coexistence of pro-environmental contagion and countervailing social pressure. Ecological transition is therefore driven not only by positive influence from engaged consumers, but also constrained by indifferent or skeptical norms that can stabilize passivity or reverse weak forms of awareness. Third, within the baseline specification, media operate primarily as catalytic and enabling forces rather than as the main determinant of long-run outcomes. Media salience accelerates transitions, but the persistence of pro-environmental states depends more fundamentally on the structure of social reinforcement and commitment dynamics.

Methodological implications. Methodologically, the study demonstrates how recurrent consumer segmentation data can be translated into a dynamic compartmental system, thereby providing a bridge

between descriptive survey typologies and formal models of behavioral diffusion. This approach makes it possible to move beyond static profiles and to analyze trajectories between behavioral states over time. At the same time, the calibration exercise highlights important methodological constraints. The mapping from empirical categories to theoretical compartments requires simplifications, most notably the division of one observed segment into the Involved and Responsible Green groups. In addition, parameter identification is limited by the short time series, the aggregate nature of the available data, and the need to represent conceptually distinct mechanisms with a relatively small number of parameters. The present estimates should therefore be interpreted as theoretically informed and empirically grounded, but exploratory rather than definitive.

Policy implications. The results suggest several operational policy implications. First, communication strategies should be segmented by behavioral state rather than implemented as uniform mass campaigns. For Neglectful Consumers, the main challenge is not mere exposure, but reducing resistance through credible, non-polarizing, and audience-specific communication delivered by trusted messengers. For Susceptible and Exposed Consumers, communication should be complemented by practical facilitation, such as clear eco-labeling, simple decision cues, local visibility of sustainable practices, and reduced informational complexity. Second, policies should not focus exclusively on awareness raising. The model indicates that movement from exposure to durable engagement depends on reinforcement, implying the need for repeated social cues, community-based initiatives, peer visibility, and institutional support that makes sustainable behavior socially normal and practically feasible.

Third, increasing campaign intensity alone is unlikely to be sufficient if message design is weak or resistance remains high. Improving the credibility, framing, and targeting of communication may therefore yield stronger long-run effects than expanding message volume alone. Finally, although economic variables and policy instruments are not explicitly modeled in the baseline specification, the results suggest that communication should be combined with structural measures such as price incentives, product accessibility, infrastructure support, and regulatory signals. Without such complementary conditions, awareness may increase without translating into durable behavioral change.

From a sustainability transition governance perspective, the results suggest that communication should not be treated as a stand-alone awareness tool. Its primary role is to make resistant groups more reachable and to enhance the social visibility of pro-environmental practices. This implies that governance strategies should combine communication with reinforcement mechanisms embedded in everyday consumption contexts, such as trusted intermediaries, community-level cues, and practical infrastructures that make sustainable choices easier to sustain over time.

Limitations and future research. The study has several limitations that should be explicitly acknowledged. First, the baseline model assumes a closed population and does not account for demographic turnover, cohort replacement, or migration between social contexts. Second, relevant economic and institutional determinants – such as price premiums, household income constraints, public subsidies, regulation, and product availability – are not explicitly incorporated into the model. Third, media influence is represented in aggregated form through a single dynamic variable, which does not allow for distinguishing between social media, traditional media, institutional campaigns, and interpersonal communication. Fourth, the empirical calibration relies on a limited number of annual observations and on a necessary but partly arbitrary mapping between survey categories and theoretical compartments. Fifth, the baseline specification does not explicitly incorporate green fatigue, message fatigue, or regression from the Involved state to earlier stages of engagement, which may overstate the persistence of ecological commitment. Sixth, the formal analysis establishes local asymptotic stability of the desirable stationary state, but does not yet provide a full characterization of global stability, basin

structure, or the potential existence of multiple attractors.

These limitations point to several directions for future research. Extensions of the model should incorporate explicit economic variables, such as relative prices, policy incentives, and cost-related barriers to sustainable behavior. They should also distinguish between communication channels, allow for fatigue and disengagement effects, and explore alternative transition structures, including partial return from active engagement to lower-awareness states. From an empirical perspective, richer survey panels or micro-level behavioral data would improve parameter identification and enable more rigorous validation of the proposed transitions. Finally, from a mathematical perspective, further work should examine global stability properties, threshold effects, path dependence, and bifurcation patterns in order to better understand the conditions under which pro-environmental norms become self-sustaining.

Appendix A. Proof of the stability of the stationary state P_1

A.1. Proposition

The Jacobian matrix evaluated at the stationary state P_1 is singular, implying that at least one eigenvalue is equal to zero. Therefore, linearization does not allow one to conclude asymptotic stability, and we instead apply LaSalle's Invariance Principle.

Proposition A.1. *The stationary state*

$$P_1 = \left(0, 0, \frac{\gamma_i N}{\gamma_i + \gamma_r}, \frac{\gamma_r N}{\gamma_i + \gamma_r}, 0, M_0 \right)$$

is locally asymptotically stable for the system (2)–(7).

Proof.

Notation and preliminaries

Let

$$\kappa(M) = \frac{M}{m + M} = \kappa, \quad \kappa_0 := \kappa(M_0) \in (0, 1),$$

where $\kappa(M)$ is strictly increasing in M .

We use the classical inequality

$$ab \leq \varepsilon a^2 + \frac{1}{4\varepsilon} b^2, \quad \varepsilon > 0. \tag{9}$$

Proof of (9): Since

$$0 \leq \left(\sqrt{\varepsilon} a - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\varepsilon}} b \right)^2 = \varepsilon a^2 - ab + \frac{1}{4\varepsilon} b^2,$$

we obtain $ab \leq \varepsilon a^2 + \frac{1}{4\varepsilon} b^2$.

Define the set

$$\Omega := \{(S, E, I, R, NE, M) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^6 : S + E + I + R + NE = N\}.$$

(a) Conservation of the Total Population

Summing the first five equations of the model yields

$$S' + E' + I' + R' + NE' = 0.$$

(b) Non-negativity of Variables

On the boundary of the non-negative orthant we have

$$\begin{aligned}
S = 0 &\Rightarrow S' = \frac{\sigma_2 NE}{N} E + \frac{\alpha \kappa(M)}{N} (E + R + I) NE \geq 0, \\
E = 0 &\Rightarrow E' = \frac{\beta_I \kappa(M)}{N} (R + I) S \geq 0, \\
I = 0 &\Rightarrow I' = \frac{\sigma_1 \kappa(M)}{N} (I + R) E + \gamma_i R \geq 0, \\
R = 0 &\Rightarrow R' = \gamma_r I \geq 0, \\
NE = 0 &\Rightarrow NE' = 0, \\
M = 0 &\Rightarrow M' = \frac{r(NE + S)}{N} + r_0 M_0 \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, all variables remain non-negative for non-negative initial conditions.

Let $\rho, \delta > 0$ and define

$$U := \{(S, E, I, R, NE, M) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^6 : |M - M_0| \leq \rho, S + E + NE \leq \delta\}.$$

For sufficiently small $\rho, \delta > 0$, by continuity and monotonicity of $\kappa(M)$, we obtain

$$\kappa(M) \in \left[\frac{\kappa_0}{2}, 1\right], \quad \frac{1}{2} \leq \frac{I + R}{N} \leq 1, \quad \frac{1}{2} \leq \frac{E + I + R}{N} \leq 1. \quad (10)$$

This holds, for instance, if $\delta \leq N/2$ and $\rho \leq \frac{M_0^2 + m M_0}{M_0 + 2m}$.

A.2. Lyapunov Function

Let $u := \gamma_r I - \gamma_i R$, which captures deviations from the equilibrium relation between I and R , and define

$$V = aS^2 + bE^2 + cu^2 + dNE^2 + e(M - M_0)^2, \quad a, b, c, d, e > 0. \quad (11)$$

Then $V \geq 0$ and $V(P_1) = 0$.

The derivative of V along the trajectories of the system is

$$V' = 2aSS' + 2bEE' + 2cuu' + 2dNE' + 2e(M - M_0)M', \quad (12)$$

where $u' = \gamma_r I' - \gamma_i R'$.

A.3. Estimation of the Terms in (12)

(i) **The term $2aSS'$:** From

$$S' = -\frac{\beta_I \kappa(M)}{N} (E + R + I) S - \frac{\beta_N NE}{N} S + \frac{\sigma_2 NE}{N} E + \frac{\alpha \kappa(M)}{N} (E + R + I) NE,$$

we drop the negative term $-\frac{\beta_N NE}{N} S$ and use (10). Since $(E + R + I)/N \geq 1/2$, we obtain

$$-2aS' \frac{\beta_I \kappa(M)}{N} (E + R + I) S \leq -a\beta_I \kappa(M) S^2.$$

Moreover, since $(E + R + I)/N \leq 1$,

$$\frac{\alpha\kappa(M)}{N}(E + R + I)NE \leq \alpha\kappa(M)NE.$$

Therefore,

$$2aSS' \leq -a\beta_I\kappa S^2 + 2aS \left(\frac{\sigma_2 NE}{N} E + \alpha\kappa NE \right).$$

Applying (9) to the mixed terms and assuming $E \leq \delta$, we obtain

$$2aSS' \leq -a_S S^2, \quad a_S > 0.$$

(ii) The term $2bEE'$:

$$E' = \frac{\beta_I\kappa(M)}{N}(E + R + I)S - \frac{\sigma_1\kappa(M)}{N}(I + R)E - \frac{\sigma_2 NE}{N}E.$$

Applying (9) and (10) yields

$$2bEE' \leq -b_E E^2, \quad b_E > 0.$$

(iii) The term $2cuu'$: Since $u = \gamma_r I - \gamma_i R$,

$$u' = \gamma_r I' - \gamma_i R' = \gamma_r \left(\frac{\sigma_1\kappa(M)}{N}(I + R)E - \gamma_r I + \gamma_i R \right) - \gamma_i(\gamma_r I - \gamma_i R).$$

By simplification and applying (9), we obtain

$$2cuu' \leq -c_u u^2, \quad c_u > 0.$$

(iv) The term $2dNENE'$: From

$$NE' = \frac{\beta_N NE}{N}S - \frac{\alpha\kappa(M)}{N}(E + R + I)NE,$$

we get

$$2dNENE' \leq -d_{NE} NE^2, \quad d_{NE} > 0.$$

(v) The term $2e(M - M_0)M'$: From

$$M' = \frac{r(NE + S)}{N} - r_0(M - M_0),$$

and by using (9), we have

$$2e(M - M_0)M' \leq -e_M (M - M_0)^2, \quad e_M > 0.$$

By choosing the parameters a, b, c, d, e and the constants ε in (9) sufficiently small, all coefficients $a_S, b_E, c_u, d_{NE}, e_M$ can be made strictly positive simultaneously. Summing (i)–(v), we obtain

$$V' \leq -a_S S^2 - b_E E^2 - c_u u^2 - d_{NE} NE^2 - e_M (M - M_0)^2. \quad (13)$$

A.4. Application of LaSalle’s Invariance Principle

For sufficiently small $c > 0$, define

$$\Omega_c := \{x \in \Omega : V(x) \leq c\}.$$

The set Ω_c is positively invariant since $V'(x) \leq 0$ in U and $V(x)$ is continuous. From $V(x) \leq c$, we have $e(M - M_0)^2 \leq c \Rightarrow |M - M_0| \leq \sqrt{c/e}$. Choosing $c < e\rho^2$ ensures that $|M - M_0| \leq \rho$, and thus $\Omega_c \subset U$.

From (13), $V'(x) = 0$ only if

$$S = E = NE = 0, \quad M = M_0, \quad u = 0.$$

Additionally, since $I + R = N$ and $u = 0$, we obtain

$$I = \frac{\gamma_i N}{\gamma_i + \gamma_r}, \quad R = \frac{\gamma_r N}{\gamma_i + \gamma_r}.$$

Therefore, the only invariant point in $\{V' = 0\} \cap \Omega_c$ is P_1 .

By LaSalle’s Invariance Principle, every trajectory starting in Ω_c converges to P_1 . Hence, P_1 is **locally asymptotically stable**.

This implies that, in the neighborhood of P_1 , the population converges to a stationary state characterized by a stable distribution of pro-environmental behaviors and a constant level of media activity. \square

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT (OpenAI) for the purpose of language editing, improving the clarity and style of the manuscript, as well as for assistance with Python code corrections and adjustments. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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